

INTERMEDIATE VIETNAMESE

VIET 203

The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

COURSE INFORMATION

Credit Hours: 3

Pre or Co-Requisites: Completion of VIET 102 or placement exam result of 203

Target Audience: All students

Meeting Pattern: MWF, 10:10 AM-11:00 AM

Instructional Format: Remote/Synchronous

Classroom: <redacted> / Passcode: <redacted>

Course Site: <redacted>

INSTRUCTOR INFORMATION

Name: Dr. Huy Phung (thầy Huy) / He/him/his

Email Address: <redacted>

Office Hours: 1:30-2:30 PM and by appointment

Office: Zoom **Zoom ID:** <redacted>

COURSE CONTENT

Course Description

This course is designed for students who have completed Elementary Vietnamese II (VIET 102) or have an equivalent level of proficiency. Building on prior knowledge, the course aims to help students reach an intermediate (low-mid) level of proficiency through a proficiency-oriented, task-based approach. Students will engage in real-world tasks and projects that provide meaningful opportunities for both linguistic input and output. The course will feature authentic materials and interactive activities to enhance students' understanding of Vietnamese grammar, vocabulary, and sociolinguistic aspects, including regional dialects and the Vietnamese diaspora.

Student Learning Outcomes

By the end of this course, students should be able to:

- Understand the main idea and key details in spoken and written texts on familiar topics, identifying relevant information, though occasional clarification may be needed.
- Participate in spontaneous conversations on familiar topics, creating simple sentences and series of sentences to ask and answer questions, with occasional pauses to search for vocabulary.
- Communicate information and make presentations on familiar topics, narrating experiences, explaining preferences, and providing basic details, despite occasional sentence fragmentation.
- Demonstrate an understanding of cultural topics, including regional dialects and the Vietnamese diaspora, navigating social interactions with increasing comfort.

Course Texts & Materials

Phung, H., Sakach, A., & Nguyen, C. (2024). *Intermediate Vietnamese: A Task-based Journey*. Open Educational Resources [<https://osf.io/a2hx4>]
<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/JHQ6N> [[view the materials website](#)]

Supplementary materials and additional hand-outs will be provided on Canvas.

COURSE ASSIGNMENTS & ASSESSMENTS

- **Active Participation (20%):** You are expected to attend all classes and to be on time. There will be a check-in session at each class meeting. It is required that you complete tasks/activities before, during, and after class as assigned and actively contribute to the class activities.
- **Exit Tasks & HW (30%):** There are three exit tasks equivalent to three modes of communication for each module. These exit tasks provide you with the opportunities to use Vietnamese in the real world. Likewise, you will be asked to complete language focused interactive activities where you can check the answers on your own.
- **Quizzes (x7) 15%:** Quizzes will be given every two weeks after each module to help you review and identify what you have or haven't learnt. These quizzes can be delivered either on paper or via Canvas. It is very important to complete interactive activities as assigned by the instructor to perform well on these quizzes.

- **Language Project (15%):** You can work in pairs or a small group on a language project. You can propose a project idea or pick up some ideas from previous classes (e.g., picture books for children, a cultural presentation, or a family newsletter). You and your team will have to report your project progress to receive feedback from the instructor and other class members.
- **Scenario-based Exam (20%):** At the end of the course, you will take a scenario-based exam. This exam will test your skills in multiple modes of communication, such as speaking, writing, and listening, in realistic scenarios (e.g., preparing for a job interview, planning a birthday party, etc.). The exam will help gauge how well you have applied what you've learned throughout the course.

Grading

Your grade will be based on the following:

- | | |
|-----------------------|-----|
| ● Participation | 20% |
| ● Exit Tasks/HW | 30% |
| ● Quizzes (x7) | 15% |
| ● Language Projects | 15% |
| ● Scenario-based Exam | 20% |

Total	100%
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Grading Scale

More information about the grading system is available on the [Registrar's website](#). The decimal place (if any) will round to the tenth decimal.

OTHER REQUIREMENTS & EXPECTATIONS

Placement/Achievement Exam

All students must complete a placement exam before attending class to ensure proper course placement. VIET101 is intended for beginners. Native speakers or those who have higher proficiency in Vietnamese are not eligible for this course. Misrepresentation of language skills from the placement exam may result in removal from the course or a failing grade. The placement exam includes written and oral components available on Canvas, which must be completed before or on the first day of class.

COURSE SCHEDULE (TENTATIVE)

TO BE UPDATED

Week	Monday	Wednesday	Friday
Week 1	Course Introduction Placement Exam (cont.)	Introductions	Introductions
Week 2	Introduction	Introductions	Quiz & Review
Week 3	Holiday (Labor Day). No classes	Daily Routines	Daily Routines
Week 4	Daily Routines	Daily Routines	Quiz & Review
Week 5	MODULE 4 Food & Drinks Task 1A. <i>Read recipes to identify the ingredients and the instructions</i> - Activities 3-4-5 - Grammar Notes HW: - Activities 6-8 - Cultural Notes - Task 1B (exit task)	MODULE 4 Food Task 1B. <i>Read and choose 2 Vietnamese recipes to share with family or friends</i> - Glossary Review HW: - Task 2A. Activities 3-4 - Task 2. Language Varieties + Cultural Note	MODULE 4 Food Task 2A. <i>Discuss to create a Street Food Showdown Challenge</i> - Activities 1-2 - Maintask Steps 1-2 - Activity 5 HW: - Activities 6-9 - Prepare for Task 2B
Week 6	MODULE 4 Food Task 2B. <i>Collaborate with others to create a street food map of Chapel Hill for Vietnamese tourists</i> - Activity 10 HW: - Task 3A. Activity 2; Maintask Steps 1-2	MODULE 4 Food Task 3A. <i>Write a restaurant review to post on social media</i> - Activity 1, 3 - Maintask Step 3 - Grammar Notes HW: - Activities 4-9 - Task 3B. Exit	MODULE 4 REVIEW Quiz on Module #4 Task 3B. <i>Create a restaurant review video for sharing on your Instagram account</i> SHOW & REFLECT Project Progress Report HW: - Module 6. Task 1A, activities 1-2-3 - Cultural Note
Week 7	MODULE 6 Health Task 1A. <i>Read to identify the youth stress causes for sharing with others</i> - Maintask Steps 1-2-3	MODULE 6 Health Task 1B. <i>Listen and note the information from 3 patients for therapist's meeting</i>	MODULE 6 Health Task 2A. <i>Discuss to design a balanced work-life model</i> - Activity 2

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity 4 - Grammar Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 5-9 - Task 1B. Listen and note the information from 3 patients for therapist's meeting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Homework Review - Language Varieties <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task 2A. Activities 1, 3 - Glossary via Quizlet 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintask Steps 1-2-3 - Activity 4 <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 6-7-8 - Cultural Notes - Task 2B. <i>Interview a Vietnamese student on managing study-abroad stress</i>
Week 8	<p>MODULE 6 Health</p> <p>Task 2B. <i>Interview a Vietnamese student on managing study-abroad stress</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share the interviews - Task 1A, activities 4-5 <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Glossary via Quizlet - Task 3A. Activities 1-2-3 - Task 3A. Maintask Step 1 	<p>MODULE 6 Health</p> <p>Task 3A. <i>Write an advice column to advise the Gen Z "Move more Sit less"</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintask Steps 2-3 - Activity 4 <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 5-10 	<p>MODULE 6 REVIEW</p> <p>Quiz on Module #6</p> <p>Task 3B. <i>Write a letter supporting your Vietnamese friend dealing with mental health issues</i></p> <p>Project Progress Report</p> <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Module 10, Task 1A. Activities 1-3; Maintask
Week 9	<p>MODULE 10 Family</p> <p>Task 1A. <i>Read a story on a family to exchange information</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repeat the main task - Activities 3, 5, 6 - Language Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 7-11 - Task 1B. Exit 	<p>MODULE 10 Family</p> <p>Task 1B. <i>Read story about family bond to retell your friends</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - share your stories - Vote for the best one <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Glossary/vocab review - Task 3A. Write a letter to your family member (Activity 1, 3 + Maintask) 	<p>MODULE 10 Family</p> <p>Task 3A. <i>Write a letter to your family member</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity 2, 4, 7 - Grammar Note <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 6-11 - Task 3B. Exit
Week 10	<p>MODULE 10 Family</p> <p>Task 3B. <i>Write a letter to your family member</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer feedback - Language Varieties - Cultural Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Send your letter - Task 2A. Activities 1-4 	<p>MODULE 10 Family</p> <p>Task 2A. <i>Discuss to make a plan for a family outing</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintask Steps 1-3 - Activity 7 - Grammar Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 6, 8, 9 - Prepare for Task 2B 	<p>MODULE 10 REVIEW</p> <p>Quiz on Module #10</p> <p>Task 2B. <i>Discuss to make a plan for a family reunion</i></p> <p>Project Progress Report</p> <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Module 8 Task 1A, activities 1-2-3 -

<p>Week 11</p>	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Task 1A. <i>Summarize a reading about Tết Nguyên Đán</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main task Steps 1-2-3 - Activity 4 - Grammar Note <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 5,6,7,8 - Task 1B. Prepare a summary table about other Tết 	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Task 1B. <i>Prepare a summary table about other Tết</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultural Note - Glossary Review <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task 2A. Activities 1-2-3, 6 - Task 2 Glossary Preview 	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Task 2A. <i>Exchange info about your personal and public celebrations</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main task Steps 1-2 - Activities 3-4 <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 7-8 - Cultural Notes - Task 2B. Interview
<p>Week 12</p>	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Task 2B. <i>Interview a Vietnamese-speaking person about Tết</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share and Reflect <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task 3A. Activities 1-2-3 - Prepare a presentation 	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Task 3A. <i>Present a unique/surprising holiday/celebration</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 4-5 - Grammar Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 6-10 - Cultural Notes - Task 3B. Exit task 	<p>MODULE 8 Holidays</p> <p>Quiz on Module #8</p> <p>Task 3B. Describe (write) a unique/special holiday/celebration</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Peer Feedback <p>Prepare for Project Presentation</p> <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Module 9, Task 1A, activities 1-2-3 + maintask
<p>Week 13</p>	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Task 1A. <i>Respond to a short story</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Repeat main task - Activities 4-5 - Grammar Notes <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 6-7-8-9 - Task 1B. Read to recommend a short story 	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Task 1B. <i>Read to recommend a short story</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share your story - Review activities <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Task 2A, activities 1-2-3 - Vocabulary preparation 	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Task 2A. <i>Discuss to create a playlist for a road trip</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main task Steps 1-2 - Activities 4-5-6 <p>HW:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 7-8-9-10 - Grammar Notes - Task 2B Preparation
<p>Week 14</p>	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Task 2B. <i>Exchange ideas to create a playlist for an event</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review previous activities 	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Task 3A. <i>Write a different ending for a story.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activities 4, 6 - Grammar Notes <p>HW:</p>	<p>MODULE 9 Entertainment</p> <p>Quiz on Module #9</p> <p>Task 3B. <i>Write a short story in Vietnamese</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share and vote <p>HW:</p>

	HW: - Task 3A. Activities 1-2-3 - Main task 3A	- Activities 7-8 - Task 3B. Write a short story in Vietnamese	- Prepare for Project Presentation
Week 15	Project Presentations	Project Presentations	Project Presentations
Week 16	REVIEW Week 1-8 Project Presentations	REVIEW Week 9-14 Project Presentations	Exam Study Guide Mock Exam/Demo
Week 17	Final Exam (2-3 hours) via Canvas (Browser Lock) Scenario-based Assessment /Integrated Performance Assessment		

Link to all the Modules/Tasks:

Phung, H., Sakach, A., & Nguyen, C. (2024). *Intermediate Vietnamese: A Task-based Journey*. Open Educational Resources [https://osf.io/a2hx4] <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/JHQ6N>